

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha⁻¹; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha⁻¹.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were *or* Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha⁻¹ at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors: four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Two varieties released for the Thambiraparani region

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Co 43 and Co 44 were recently released for general cultivation in Thambiraparani. They were developed at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore. Co 43 is a cross of Dasal and IR20, and Co 44 is a cross of ASD5 and IR20. Both are medium-duration (128 d) semidwarfs with

medium slender white grains.

From 1981 to 1983 they were evaluated in three (Sep-Oct to Feb) yield trials at Ambasamudram. Trials were fertilized with 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha.

Both varieties performed better than IR20. Co 43 yielded an average 3.9 t/ha; and Co 44, 3.7 t/ha (see table). Co 43 is resistant to saline/alkaline conditions, leaf blast (Bl), sheath rot, and bacterial leaf blight. Co 44 is moderately resistant to brown spot, Bl, and sheath blight, and resistant to green leafhopper and gall midge. □

Performance of Co 43 and Co 44 at Ambasamudram, India.

Variety	Days to flowering	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
					MLT ^a	ART ^b	PC ^c	Mean
Co 43	98	87	6	1.8	4.0	4.6	3.2	3.9
Co 44	98	86	6	1.2	3.6	4.3	3.1	3.7
IR20	97	89	5	1.3	3.1	3.3	2.8	3.1
CD P = (0.05)					—	0.5	0.8	

^aMultilocation trial. ^bAdaptive research trial. ^cPromising cultures.

Two IRRI rice lines released for cultivation in the Cuu Long Delta

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IRRI rice lines IR9224-73-2-2-2-3 and IR8423-132-6-2-2 were released in 1983 for large-scale cultivation in the Cuu Long

Delta of Vietnam.

IR9224-73-2-2-2-3 was named OM33. It has short growth duration, heavy tillering, many grains/panicle (Table 1, 2), and good quality. It yields well in wet and dry seasons.

IR8423-132-6-2-2 is early maturing and has many grains/panicle and low sterility percentage in wet season (Table 1). In experimental plots and farmer fields it yields better in wet than in dry

Table 1. Agronomic traits of IR9224-73-2-2-2-3 and IR8423-132-6-2-2 at Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam.

Trait	IR9224-73-2-2-2-3		IR8423-132-6-2-2	
	1981-82 wet season	1982-83 dry season	1981-82 wet season	1982-83 dry season
Duration (d)	115	110	115	113
Plant height (cm)	107	90	103	87
Panicles/m ²	305	396	250	326
Grains/panicle	88	95	100	92
Sterility (0/0)	22.2	15.5	12.5	18.2
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.6	23.4	22.5	23.0

Table 2. Yields of IR9224-73-2-2-3 and IR8423-132-6-2-2 at Omon. Haugiang, Vietnam.

Line, variety	Yield (t/ha)				Av
	Wet season		Dry season		
	1981	1982	1982	1983	
IR9224-73-2-2-3	6.1	4.5	4.2	6.5	5.3
IR8423-132-6-2-2	6.7	3.9	3.5	5.5	4.9
Check ^a	5.7	3.3	4.2	4.7	4.5
LSD 50/0	0.51	0.57	ns	0.85	

^aCheck variety: wet season 1981, NN 6A; other seasons, NN 7A.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Ratooning ability of some summer rices on saline-calcareous soil

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We conducted a field trial in summer 1979 at RAU Research Farm to determine the ratooning ability of Pusa 2-2 1, CR44-35, Pusa 33, NC1626, CR126-42-2, IET1444, and C8585. Soil was a calcareous silt loam with medium fertility, pH 8.7, and Ec 1.20 mmho/cm at 25°C.

Seeds were sown 16 Mar and 2 seedlings/hill were transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing on 19 Apr. The main crop received 120-18-17 kg NPK/ha. C8585 was harvested 16 Jul, NC1626 19 Jul, and other varieties were harvested 1 wk earlier, leaving a 15-cm stubble from ground level. The ratoon crop was hand weeded 15 d after the main crop was harvested, and 20 kg N/ha was top-dressed. The field remained saturated with occasional flooding up to 10-cm

depth. The crop was irrigated twice in addition to frequent monsoon rains. At maturity, the ratoon crop of NC1626 (intermediate) and C8585 (semidwarf) was harvested. Yields of other varieties were not recorded because of their poor ratooning ability.

The C8585 ratoon yielded 32% of the main crop yield, and NC1626 24% of its main crop yield (see table). When yields of the main and ratoon crops were combined, however, NC1626 yielded better overall.

The ratoon crop was 25% shorter than the main crop. Panicle-bearing shoots/hill of the ratoon seemed to be positively correlated with the number of panicle-bearing shoots/hill for the main crop. The reduction in the number of ripened grains/panicle of ratoon was more pronounced (20-26%) than panicle length reduction (8-11%). The ratoon crop had lower grain weight (more with NC 1626) than the main crop. The ratoon crop matured 70 d earlier than the main crop.

Grain yield, yield attributes, and other plant characters of main and ratoon crops of 2 short-duration summer rices, Bihar, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Panicles/m ^{2a}	Grains/panicle (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Duration (d)
NC1626 Main crop	4.1	131	444 (10)	95	20.5	21.6	125
NC1626 Ratoon	1.0	102	222 (5)	76	18.2	20.5	54
C8585 Main crop	3.5	90	488 (11)	84	19.1	19.8	122
C8585 Ratoon	1.1	65	311 (7)	62	17.5	19.2	52

^aFigures in parentheses indicate number of panicles/hill.

season. It has yielded well in many provinces.

Like previously released IRRI lines NN3A (IR36), NN6A (IR2307-247-2-2-3), and NN7A (IR2070-199-3-6-6), both newly released lines are resistant to most rice pests on the Delta except blast. They can be grown on slightly acid sulfate and saline soils. □

In Bihar, farmers usually plant one crop of early rice on medium uplands in wet season to ensure timely planting of subsequent upland crops. Besides increasing rice yield with less expenditure, growing a ratoon crop still permits timely planting of upland crops. Irrigation availability is, however, a prerequisite for a ratoon crop in this area. □

Mashuri for cultivation in the Cuu Long Delta of Vietnam

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Much of the Cuu Long River Delta (Vietnamese part of the Mekong Delta) still is planted to late-maturing local varieties which yield from 1.5 to 4 t/ha. We compared Mashuri, introduced through the International Rice Testing Program in 1980, with popular local varieties Trang Chum (deepwater), Trang Lun (acid sulfate tolerant), Tieu Doil (salinity tolerant), and Nang Huong (good quality). In 3 yr of evaluation, Mashuri yielded well (Table 1). It had shorter duration than local varieties, produced more grains/panicle, and had lodging resistance, wide adaptability, and good quality.

Mashuri, Trang Chum, and Trang Lun react similarly to common rice pests of the Cuu Long Delta. They are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) and sheath blight (ShB) and tolerant of leaf blast